

Demographic and Organizational Factors as Correlate of Artificial Intelligence Adoption among Banks in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the influence of demographic and organizational factors as correlate of the adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) among accounting practitioners in Nigeria. A cross-sectional survey design was adopted, and a structured questionnaire served as the primary instrument for data collection, administered to employees of five (5) Tier-1 banks representing the most capitalized institutions in the Nigerian banking industry. The Krejcie and Morgan sample size determination table was utilized to determine the sample size by ensuring adequate representation of the target population. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (such as frequency counts, means, standard deviations, skewness, and kurtosis), regression diagnostic tests (variance inflation factor), and inferential statistics (simple regression analysis). The findings revealed that both demographic factors ($F = 157.70$, $p < 0.05$) and organizational factors ($F = 351.67$, $p < 0.05$) significantly influence the adoption of artificial intelligence among accounting practitioners in Nigeria. Consequently, the study concludes that demographic and organizational characteristics are key determinants of AI adoption in the accounting profession. It recommends that accounting practitioners should complement their technical accounting expertise with technological proficiency, data analysis skills, and adaptability to emerging innovations. Organizations are further encouraged to continuously retrain their employees to enhance technological awareness, strengthen competencies, and promote alignment with evolving digital practices that support the achievement of organizational objectives.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence; Accounting practitioners; Demographic factors
Commercial banks; Organizational factors;

JEL Classification: M41; M49

INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly reshaping global industries, earning widespread recognition for its potential to enhance efficiency, precision, and competitiveness across sectors where it has been adopted (Emetaram & Uchime, 2021). In the accounting profession, the growing demand for accuracy and efficiency in processing complex financial data has given rise to the need for the integration of AI into accounting systems and practices. The adoption of AI and other emerging accounting technologies has significantly minimized manual accounting tasks and traditional bookkeeping activities. However, despite its transformative potential worldwide, the use of AI among accounting practitioners in Nigeria remains relatively low. This slow adoption is influenced by a range of determinants, including demographic factors, organizational characteristics, technological infrastructure, and the prevailing legal and regulatory environment.

Although AI adoption in accounting offers clear advantages such as improved accuracy, cost

and time efficiency, fraud detection, risk management, and data-driven insights it has been reported that a good number of firms have been reluctant to fully embracing AI solutions (Emetaram & Uchime, 2021; Hassani & MacFeely, 2023; Adelekan et al., 2024). Key barriers include differences in age, gender, and educational background; variations in professional experience; fear of job redundancy; low levels of digital literacy; inadequate technological infrastructure; high implementation costs; restricted access to AI-based accounting software; regulatory uncertainties; and limited technical expertise. These challenges collectively contribute to the sluggish pace of AI integration within Nigeria's accounting landscape.

Moreover, heightened concerns regarding data privacy, cybersecurity, and inadequate digital skills have further slowed AI adoption. The absence of a coherent policy framework or well-defined regulatory guidelines for AI application within the accounting sector exacerbates this hesitation, creating uncertainty among practitioners. This regulatory ambiguity makes it difficult for firms to fully commit to AI-driven innovations, leaving many at a disadvantage in an increasingly technology-oriented global financial environment. Without structured policies to support AI adoption, Nigerian accounting professionals risk lagging behind their international counterparts in leveraging AI for strategic advantage (Oyedokun, Anyahara, & Oyedokun, 2025). This study aims to provide a deeper understanding of both the challenges and opportunities surrounding AI integration in Nigeria's accounting profession. Its findings are expected to guide policymakers, regulators, and professional accounting bodies in developing frameworks that promote AI adoption and digital transformation within the sector. By identifying key demographic and organizational determinants, the study seeks to enhance the readiness of accounting practitioners to adapt to the evolving digital ecosystem.

Existing literature indicates that most prior studies on accounting practitioners' perceptions of AI adoption have focused primarily on small and medium-sized enterprises (Rawashdeh, Bakhit & Abaalkhail, 2023; Bhalerao, Lee & Tajudeen, 2020; Chatterjee, Chaudhuri, Vrontis, Soumya & Ghosh, 2021). While these studies provide useful insights, their scope is limited and often context-specific, with minimal attention paid to large firms or the unique challenges within the Nigerian environment. Furthermore, the limited Nigerian studies available have been largely exploratory or qualitative in nature (Ogunbangbe & Kalu, 2024; Oladele, Akinsola, Afrogha, Wright & Oyewole, 2021), while the more robust quantitative analyses have predominantly originated from developed economies. To bridge this research gap, the present study empirically investigates the extent to which organizational and demographic factors influence the adoption of AI among accounting practitioners in Nigeria. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: a review of related literature, methodology, data analysis and results, followed by the conclusion and recommendations.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Artificial Intelligence Adoption

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been defined in several ways, yet all definitions converge on one central concept the ability of machines to learn, reason, and perform tasks that traditionally require human intelligence. Haenlein and Kaplan (2019) describe AI as a system capable of accurately interpreting external data, learning from it, and applying what it has learned to achieve specific objectives through adaptive transformation. Similarly, Chukwudi (2018) explains that AI empowers machines to execute tasks once considered exclusive to the human

mind including acquiring knowledge, understanding relationships, exercising judgment, and demonstrating creativity (Oyedokun, Anyahara, & Oyedokun, 2025). These capabilities illustrate AI's growing role as a substitute for human reasoning and decision-making in complex tasks.

From a business standpoint, AI involves the deployment of technologies such as machine learning, natural language processing, and computer vision to enhance business operations, improve employee productivity, and create organizational value (Petkov, 2020). According to Peng and Chang (2019), by the year 2035, organizations utilizing AI are projected to be 40% more efficient than those relying on traditional methods, emphasizing AI's transformative potential for modern enterprises. In accounting, this transformation has been particularly evident. The manual accounting systems of two decades ago dominated by paper-based ledgers, repetitive data entry, and intensive human effort have increasingly been replaced by automated, technology-driven systems. While traditional methods proved reliable over time, they were laborious, prone to error, and inefficient in managing large datasets.

The inherent limitations of manual accounting, such as slow processing and restricted analytical capacity, have heightened the demand for automation and digital solutions. As Ogunbangbe and Kalu (2024) noted, these inefficiencies hinder timely financial reporting and compromise accuracy. Consequently, AI has emerged as a revolutionary force in accounting, redefining conventional practices and enabling accountants to focus on higher-value activities such as financial analysis, strategic planning, and decision support. Through AI integration, accounting has evolved from record-keeping to intelligent financial management driven by real-time insights and predictive analytics.

However, despite AI's transformative potential and the efficiency gains it promises, its adoption among Nigerian accounting professionals remains limited. Many firms still rely heavily on traditional systems, with only a few integrating AI-driven solutions into their operations. This slow adoption can be attributed to several factors, including lack of awareness, cost of implementation, and limited exposure to AI applications within the accounting context (Oyedokun, 2025). These factors collectively hinder the widespread utilization of AI and delay the transition toward digital accounting practices in Nigeria.

In Nigeria, the uptake of AI technology within the accounting profession is still in its infancy, reflecting varying degrees of awareness, preparedness, and adoption among practitioners. While AI offers opportunities such as improved accuracy, enhanced fraud detection, and streamlined reporting, it also presents challenges related to cost, infrastructure, and skill gaps. The successful adoption of AI therefore depends on both individual and institutional factors including the demographic characteristics of practitioners, organizational culture, technological readiness, and supportive regulatory frameworks.

This study focuses specifically on demographic and organizational determinants of AI adoption among accounting practitioners in Nigeria. By exploring how factors such as age, education, experience, and organizational support influence adoption decisions, the study seeks to provide empirical insight into why AI integration remains uneven across the Nigerian accounting landscape. Understanding these dynamics is essential for developing strategies that promote technological advancement and ensure the profession's competitiveness in an increasingly

digital global economy.

2.2 Demographic Factors

As advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) and related technologies continue to accelerate, demographic factors increasingly shape the readiness and ability of professionals to integrate AI into their work. Among accounting practitioners in Nigeria, these demographic characteristics significantly influence the extent of AI adoption, its practical use, and its overall effectiveness. This study examines how key demographic variables such as age, gender, educational background, work experience, technological proficiency, and professional certification affect the decision to adopt or reject AI-driven tools in accounting practice.

Age remains one of the most influential demographic factors in technology adoption. Younger accounting professionals are generally more receptive to AI due to their familiarity with digital platforms and exposure to modern technological trends. In contrast, older practitioners may display resistance to AI integration, often due to apprehension about job redundancy, discomfort with emerging technologies, or limited digital literacy. Similarly, gender plays an important role in technology acceptance. Research suggests that male practitioners often demonstrate higher rates of AI adoption compared to their female counterparts a disparity linked to societal norms, unequal access to technical training, and differences in confidence levels when using digital tools.

Educational background also contributes significantly to AI adoption. Practitioners with advanced qualifications particularly those who have studied accounting, finance, or information technology are more likely to appreciate the benefits of AI and integrate it into their professional activities. Exposure to AI-related courses and digital accounting systems during academic training enhances awareness and fosters openness to adoption. Work experience, on the other hand, produces varying effects. Mid-career accountants often combine traditional and AI-driven practices, while early-career professionals tend to adopt AI more readily. Highly experienced accountants, however, may resist change due to comfort with established methods and skepticism toward automation.

Professional certification and continuous training also play a critical role in shaping AI adoption attitudes. Certifications from professional bodies such as ICAN and ACCA increasingly incorporate technology-related competencies, preparing practitioners for the digital transformation of the accounting profession. Continuous professional development (CPD) programs and AI-focused training initiatives further strengthen practitioners' confidence and proficiency in using AI tools. Owonifari, Igbekoyi, Awotomilusi, and Dagunduro (2023), as well as Ogunbangbe and Kalu (2024), emphasize that professional exposure and targeted training are strong predictors of technology acceptance and usage among accountants.

However, despite the growing importance of AI, policy makers in developing economies, including Nigeria, remain concerned about its unintended consequences. Ukpong (2022) and Dagunduro, Falana, Adewara, and Busayo (2023) note that fears surrounding job redundancy and graduate unemployment often fuel hesitation toward full-scale AI adoption. These concerns highlight the need for a strategic policy response that emphasizes reskilling and curriculum reform. Updating educational curricula to include AI literacy and digital

competencies is crucial to preparing future accounting professionals for the evolving landscape of the profession (Oyedokun, 2025).

Notably, the Nigerian banking sector provides a glimpse of how AI can be effectively integrated into organizational processes. As Agidi (2019) observes, banks in Nigeria have significantly leveraged AI-driven technologies for process automation, customer service enhancement, and operational efficiency. Applications such as virtual customer assistants, fraud detection systems, loss prediction models, and compliance monitoring tools have demonstrated the potential of AI to transform financial operations. These developments underscore the importance of understanding demographic influences on AI adoption, as they ultimately determine how quickly and effectively such innovations can be diffused across the accounting profession in Nigeria.

2.3 Organizational Factors

Organizational factors play a crucial role in determining the adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) among accounting practitioners in Nigeria. Over time, researchers have expressed growing concern about how these factors either facilitate or hinder AI integration within accounting firms. Rawashdeh, Bakhit, and Abaalkhail (2023) categorize organizational factors influencing AI adoption into internal and external dimensions. Internal factors include an organization's openness to innovation, willingness to embrace change, and the level of leadership commitment toward AI adoption. The support of top management, particularly in allocating adequate financial and technical resources, is vital for successful implementation. Additionally, the availability of skilled personnel, access to continuous training and development programs, and adequate budgetary provisions for AI investment greatly determine the extent to which AI can be integrated into accounting operations.

Externally, factors such as competitive pressure, client expectations, and vendor support also influence the decision to adopt AI technologies. Competitive pressure arises when rival firms deploy AI tools to gain operational efficiency and service quality advantages, compelling others to follow suit. Similarly, as clients increasingly demand AI-driven solutions and data-driven insights, firms without such capabilities risk losing relevance. Vendor support, in terms of access to reliable AI tools, technical expertise, and post-implementation assistance, further enhances adoption success. Moreover, the organizational structure whether a firm operates as a public practice or a private entity affects its readiness and flexibility in adopting AI (Ahmad & Mustafa, 2022; Chukwani & Egiyi, 2020; Oyedokun, Anyahara, & Oyedokun, 2025). Public organizations may experience bureaucratic constraints, while private firms often display more agility in embracing technological innovation.

To address these challenges, accounting practitioners and organizations in Nigeria must establish comprehensive AI strategies that align with their operational goals and capabilities. This involves investing in employee training and professional development to enhance technological competence, fostering partnerships with AI solution providers, and instituting effective change management frameworks. Regular monitoring of industry trends, competitor activities, and technological advancements will also help firms remain adaptive and proactive. Ultimately, creating a culture that values innovation, supported by strong leadership commitment and resource allocation, is essential for achieving sustainable AI adoption in Nigeria's accounting sector.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the integration of the Technological Acceptance Model (TAM) and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). These theoretical frameworks provide structured lenses for examining the various factors demographic, organizational, technological, and regulatory that either facilitate or hinder the adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) among accounting practitioners in Nigeria. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Davis (1989), is one of the most widely applied models in technology adoption research. It posits that two primary factors determine users' acceptance of new technology: Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEU). Perceived usefulness refers to the extent to which accountants believe AI can improve their efficiency, accuracy, and decision-making capabilities, while perceived ease of use assesses how simple and user-friendly they find AI systems to integrate into their professional workflows. Thus, TAM suggests that if AI technologies are perceived as both beneficial and easy to use, accountants in Nigeria are more likely to adopt them.

Complementing TAM, the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), developed by Venkatesh, Morris, Davis, and Davis (2003) (as cited in Peng & Chang, 2019), expands the TAM framework by introducing additional determinants of technology adoption. These include social influence, which examines how peers, professional associations, and regulatory bodies affect individuals' willingness to adopt AI, and facilitating conditions, which refer to the availability of supportive infrastructure, technical assistance, and training opportunities necessary for successful AI implementation. UTAUT emphasizes that beyond personal perceptions, external and contextual factors significantly shape technology acceptance and usage intentions.

In the context of this study, the integration of TAM and UTAUT provides a holistic understanding of AI adoption among Nigerian accountants. While TAM captures individual perceptions of AI's usefulness and usability, UTAUT extends the analysis to organizational and environmental factors such as institutional support, professional norms, and policy frameworks. Together, these theories form a comprehensive foundation for assessing the multidimensional influences on AI adoption, highlighting the interplay between human behavior, organizational readiness, and technological capability within Nigeria's accounting profession.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design, deemed appropriate because it enables data collection from a sample drawn from a defined population at a single point in time, providing a clear snapshot of the characteristics under investigation. This design was chosen for its practicality and flexibility, as it allows for data to be gathered efficiently through multiple modes such as online, telephone, or in-person administration while offering the advantage of capturing diverse opinions and behaviors within a relatively short period. The design's suitability lies in its ability to examine relationships among variables without requiring longitudinal tracking, making it particularly effective for analyzing technology adoption patterns among accounting practitioners.

The population of this study comprised employees of the five Tier 1 commercial banks in Nigeria, selected because these institutions are the most capitalized in the banking sector and have made significant investments in Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies to streamline operations and enhance service delivery. According to available records from the banks, the total population of employees across these institutions is 45,985. To determine a representative sample, the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination table was utilized, yielding a sample size of 381 respondents. This approach ensures that the study maintains statistical representativeness and generalizability while balancing practicality and precision in data collection.

Primary data was obtained using a self-structured questionnaire designed on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 = *Strongly Disagree* to 5 = *Strongly Agree*. This scaling technique facilitated respondents' expression of their level of agreement or disagreement with each item. To establish the reliability of the research instrument, a test-retest method was conducted using 25 staff members of Unity Bank Nigeria Plc, which was not part of the study's sample. The data collected from the pilot test were analyzed using Cronbach's alpha reliability statistics, producing coefficients above the acceptable benchmark: $r = 0.74$ for demographic factors, $r = 0.83$ for organizational factors, and $r = 0.93$ for AI adoption indicating high internal consistency. In line with the study's variables, a mathematical model was formulated to express the relationship among demographic factors, organizational factors, and the adoption of Artificial Intelligence;

$$AIADOP_{it} = B_0 + B_1DMF + U_{it} \text{-----eq 1}$$

$$AIADOP_{it} = B_0 + B_1ORGF + U_{it} \text{-----eq 2}$$

Where: AIADOP = AI ADOPTION; DMF = Demographic Factors; ORGF = Organizational factors; B_0 = intercept; B_1 = Coefficient of independent variable; U_{it} = Error term.

Data obtained were analyzed via descriptive statistic (simple percentages, frequency counts, mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum value, skewness, kurtosis and Pearson correlation), regression diagnostic statistics (variance inflation factor, and Breusch-Pagan and Cook-Weisberg,) and inferential statistics (simple regression).

RESULTS

Table 1: Analysis of Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Ite ms	Variables	Parameter	Frequency =	Percent (%)
			366	
1	Gender	Male	217	59.29%
		Female	149	40.71%
		Total	366	100.00%

2	Age Brackets	20-30years	77	21.04%
		31-40years	158	43.17%
		41-50years	66	18.03%
		51-60years	44	12.02%
		61years & above	21	5.74%
		Total	366	100.00%
3	Educational Qualification	PhD	14	3.83%
		M.Sc. & Postgraduate Diploma	224	61.20%
		B.Sc.	109	29.78%
		OND/HND	17	4.64%
		Secondary Education	2	0.55%
		Total	366	100.00%
4	Area of Specialization	Financial Accounting & Reporting	128	34.97%
		Internal Auditing	48	13.11%
		External Auditing	31	8.47%
		Management Auditing	29	7.92%
		Tax Accounting	63	17.21%
		Advisory and Consulting	12	3.28%
		Others	55	15.03%
		Total	366	100.00%
5	Work Experience	Less than 1 year	33	9.02%
		1-3years	121	33.06%
		4-6years	87	23.77%
		7-10years	39	10.66%
		More than 10years	86	23.50%
		Total	366	100.00%
6	Professional Qualifications	ICAN	48	13.11%
		ANAN	52	14.21%
		ACCA	20	5.46%
		CIMA	30	8.20%
		Others	127	34.70%
		N/A	89	24.32%
		Total	366	100.00%

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

The demographic characteristics of the respondents, as presented in Table 1, provide a detailed overview of the composition of the study's participants across key variables such as gender, age, education, area of specialization, work experience, and professional qualifications. Out of a total of 366 respondents, 59.29% were male, while 40.71% were female. This distribution indicates that the majority of accounting practitioners surveyed were men, suggesting a moderate gender imbalance within the Nigerian accounting workforce, particularly among those exposed to or involved with Artificial Intelligence (AI) adoption.

In terms of age distribution, the table shows that the largest proportion of respondents (43.17%) fell within the 31–40 years age bracket, followed by 21.04% within the 20–30 years range. Respondents aged 41–50 years accounted for 18.03%, while 12.02% were between 51–60 years, and only 5.74% were 61 years and above. This age distribution reveals that most participants are relatively young or in their mid-career stage, reflecting an active and dynamic workforce that is likely to be receptive to technological innovations such as AI.

Regarding educational qualification, the results indicate a highly educated sample. A majority (61.20%) of respondents possessed either an M.Sc. or Postgraduate Diploma, followed by 29.78% holding a Bachelor's degree (B.Sc.), and 4.64% with an OND/HND qualification. A small proportion (3.83%) held a Ph.D., while 0.55% had only secondary education. This shows that the respondents are generally well-qualified, which aligns with the professional standards required in the accounting sector and suggests that the population studied has the intellectual and academic foundation necessary for engaging with AI technologies.

The area of specialization among respondents was quite diverse. The largest group (34.97%) specialized in Financial Accounting and Reporting, followed by Tax Accounting (17.21%), Internal Auditing (13.11%), External Auditing (8.47%), and Management Auditing (7.92%). A smaller proportion (3.28%) were involved in Advisory and Consulting, while 15.03% fell under the 'Others' category. This distribution highlights the multi-faceted nature of accounting practice in Nigeria and indicates that AI adoption may influence various subfields differently, depending on the nature of their operations and reliance on data-driven processes.

In terms of work experience, most respondents (33.06%) had 1–3 years of professional experience, followed by 23.77% with 4–6 years, 23.50% with more than 10 years, and 10.66% with 7–10 years of experience. A smaller group (9.02%) had less than one year of work experience. This distribution suggests a well-balanced representation across early-career and seasoned professionals, which provides a diverse perspective on AI adoption tendencies based on exposure and professional maturity.

Finally, regarding professional qualifications, the table reveals that ICAN (13.11%) and ANAN (14.21%) members made up a significant portion of the respondents, while 5.46% held ACCA certifications and 8.20% were affiliated with CIMA. A larger share (34.70%) of respondents indicated 'Others', possibly representing alternative professional bodies or non-certified practitioners, while 24.32% reported no affiliation (N/A) with any professional body. This mix underscores the diverse professional landscape within Nigeria's accounting sector, showing a combination of local and international affiliations that could influence openness to adopting AI technologies in professional practice.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Responses on Demographic Factor of AI

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. Dev	Obs.
1	The age of a personnel affects his/her willingness to adopt AI tools	3.303	1.259	366
2	Gender significantly affects personnel engagement with AI-based systems	2.800	1.124	366
3	The educational level of a personnel influences his/her ability to understand AI-systems	3.450	1.335	366
4	The years of experience of staff significantly impact on their readiness to adopt AI tools	3.368	1.150	366
5	Geographical location affects personnel's access to AI tools and training	3.439	1.168	366

Fieldwork, 2025

Table 2 summarizes respondents' views on how demographic factors influence the adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) among accounting practitioners in Nigeria. The mean scores, which range from 2.800 to 3.450, show a moderate level of agreement that demographic characteristics play an important role in shaping AI adoption behaviour. The results suggest that while certain factors such as education, experience, and geographical location have a stronger influence, others like age and gender are less decisive.

Among the variables, education had the highest mean score (3.450), indicating that higher educational qualifications enhance the ability to understand and use AI systems effectively. Work experience (mean = 3.368) and geographical location (mean = 3.439) were also found to moderately influence AI adoption, suggesting that exposure and access to resources affect readiness to embrace technology. Conversely, gender (mean = 2.800) had the least influence, implying that both male and female practitioners have similar levels of engagement with AI systems.

Overall, the findings reveal that demographic factors such as educational background, professional experience, and location significantly shape accountants' readiness and ability to adopt AI tools in Nigeria. Age plays a moderate role, while gender differences appear minimal, highlighting that access to training, infrastructure, and education are more critical determinants of AI adoption than inherent personal characteristics.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Responses on Organizational Factor of AI

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. Dev	Obs.
1	The leadership style adopted by our bank supports AI adoption	3.595	1.012	366
2	The existing organizational culture in our bank encourages technological innovation	3.614	1.091	366
3	The bank allocates sufficient financial resources for AI adoption	3.360	1.098	366
4	There is adequate IT infrastructure available to support AI initiatives	3.371	1.126	366
5	The bank has personnel with the requisite expertise for AI implementation	3.448	1.039	366

Fieldwork, 2025

Table 3 illustrates respondents' perceptions of organizational factors influencing Artificial Intelligence (AI) adoption among accounting practitioners in Nigerian banks. The findings show that key elements such as leadership style, organizational culture, financial resources, IT infrastructure, and employee expertise significantly impact the implementation of AI technologies. With mean scores ranging between 3.360 and 3.614, respondents generally agreed that leadership commitment and an innovation-driven culture play the most crucial roles in driving AI adoption. Banks with leaders who promote technological advancement and cultivate a culture of creativity and openness tend to achieve higher engagement with AI systems.

Overall, the results indicate that while Nigerian banks have made progress in fostering supportive leadership and cultivating innovation, challenges remain in ensuring adequate financial investment, robust IT infrastructure, and continuous employee training. Personnel expertise was found to be moderately sufficient, highlighting the need for regular capacity-building initiatives. In summary, organizational factors especially leadership support, innovative culture, and technical competence are key enablers of AI adoption, but sustained investment and strategic alignment are essential for maximizing AI's potential within the Nigerian banking sector.

Table 4: Pearson Correlation

	Aiadop	Dmf	Orgf	Obs
Aiadop	1.0000			366
Dmf	0.5498	1.0000		366
Orgf	0.7010	0.5863	1.0000	366

Fieldwork, 2025

Table 4 presents the results of the Pearson correlation analysis showing the relationship between Artificial Intelligence adoption (Aiadop), demographic factors (Dmf), and organizational factors (Orgf) among accounting practitioners in Nigerian banks. The

correlation coefficients measure the strength and direction of the linear relationship between these variables, with values ranging from -1 to +1. A positive correlation indicates that as one variable increases, the other tends to increase as well. From the table, the correlation between AI adoption and demographic factors is 0.5498, which represents a moderate positive relationship. This means that changes in demographic characteristics such as age, gender, education, and work experience moderately influence the likelihood of AI adoption among practitioners. In other words, practitioners’ demographic attributes play a noticeable, though not dominant, role in shaping their readiness and ability to integrate AI tools into their professional activities.

The correlation between AI adoption and organizational factors is 0.7010, indicating a strong positive relationship. This suggests that organizational elements such as leadership support, innovation culture, infrastructure, and employee expertise have a more substantial effect on AI adoption compared to demographic factors. It implies that the more supportive and technologically equipped an organization is, the higher the tendency for employees to embrace AI technologies in their work. Additionally, the correlation between demographic factors and organizational factors is 0.5863, reflecting a moderate to strong positive relationship. This shows that demographic characteristics and organizational conditions are somewhat interrelated—organizations with younger, well-educated, and tech-oriented employees may also have better structures and resources that promote innovation and technology adoption. In summary, Table 4 reveals that while both demographic and organizational factors positively influence AI adoption, organizational factors exert a stronger impact. This underscores the importance of leadership commitment, resource allocation, and institutional support in fostering effective and sustainable AI integration within Nigerian banks.

Table 5: Skewness and Kurtosis Results for Normality of Data

	Aiadop	Dmf	Orgf	Obs
Kurtosis	2.4705	3.3040	3.4165	366
Skewness	-0.3809	-0.3519	-0.6814	366

Fieldwork, 2025

Table 5 summarizes the skewness and kurtosis results used to assess the normality of data distribution for the three main variables; AI adoption (Aiadop), demographic factors (Dmf), and organizational factors (Orgf). The skewness values of -0.3809, -0.3519, and -0.6814 respectively, indicate a slight left skew, suggesting that the data are fairly symmetrical and within the acceptable range of -1 to +1. This means that there is no major deviation from normality in terms of data symmetry across the variables.

Similarly, the kurtosis values of 2.4705, 3.3040, and 3.4165 are close to the benchmark value of 3, implying a near-normal (mesokurtic) distribution. These slightly higher values indicate a modestly peaked (leptokurtic) tendency, showing that the data are somewhat concentrated around the mean but without extreme outliers. Overall, the findings confirm that the data for all variables are approximately normally distributed, satisfying the normality assumption required for further statistical analyses such as correlation and regression.

Table 6: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) Result

Variables	VIF	1/VIF
Orgf	3.17	0.3138
Dmf	1.56	0.6427
Mean VIF	2.36	

Fieldwork, 2025

Table 6 presents the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) results used to test for multicollinearity among the independent variables Organizational Factors (Orgf) and Demographic Factors (Dmf). Multicollinearity occurs when two or more predictor variables in a regression model are highly correlated, which can distort the estimated relationships between predictors and the dependent variable. The VIF measures how much the variance of a regression coefficient is inflated due to multicollinearity, while the inverse of VIF (1/VIF) indicates the proportion of variance not explained by other predictors. From the table, Orgf has a VIF of 3.17 (1/VIF = 0.3138) and Dmf has a VIF of 1.56 (1/VIF = 0.6427). Both values are well below the commonly accepted threshold of 10 (see Izukwe & Jeroh, 2022; Jeroh, 2023), and even the more conservative threshold of 5, suggesting that no serious multicollinearity problem exists among the variables. This means that the independent variables are not highly correlated with each other and can be included together in the regression model without distorting the results. The mean VIF value of 2.36 further supports this conclusion, indicating a generally low level of interdependence among the predictors. Overall, the results suggest that the regression model satisfies the assumption of no multicollinearity, ensuring that the estimated coefficients will be statistically reliable and that each independent variable contributes uniquely to explaining variations in AI adoption among accounting practitioners in Nigerian banks.

Table 7: Linear Regression for Demographic Factors and AI Adoption

Source	SS	Df	MS	Number of Obs.	=	366
Model	100.145	1	100.145	F(1, 364)	=	157.70
Residual	231.151	364	0.6350	Prob. > F	=	0.0000
Total	331.297	365	0.9076	R-Squared Adjusted	=	0.3004
Aidop	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-value	p-value		
Dmf	0.6813	0.0542	12.56	0.000		
_cons	1.1634	0.1818	6.40	0.000		

Fieldwork, 2025

Table 7 summarizes the linear regression analysis exploring the influence of demographic factors (Dmf) on Artificial Intelligence adoption (AIadop) among accounting practitioners in Nigerian banks. The results show that the model is statistically significant (F = 157.70, p = 0.000), indicating that demographic variables meaningfully affect AI adoption. With an R-squared value of 0.302 (Adjusted R² = 0.3004), the model explains about 30% of the variation in AI adoption, suggesting that while demographic factors are important, other factors also contribute to the adoption process.

The regression coefficient for demographic factors ($\beta = 0.6813$, $p < 0.01$) is positive and significant, meaning that favorable demographic characteristics such as higher education, younger age, and greater technological experience are linked to higher AI adoption levels. The constant value (1.1634, p = 0.000) further implies a moderate baseline tendency toward AI

usage, even without demographic influences. Overall, the findings indicate that demographic characteristics significantly and positively shape how accounting practitioners in Nigerian banks adopt and utilize AI technologies.

Table 8: Linear Regression for Organizational Factors and AI Adoption

Source	SS	Df	MS	Number of Obs.	=	366
Model	162.794	1	162.794	F(1, 364)	=	351.67
Residual	168.502	364	0.46291	Prob. > F	=	0.0000
Total	331.297	365	0.9076	R-Squared Adjusted	=	0.4900
Aidop	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-value	p-value		
Orgf	0.7649	0.0479	18.75	0.000		
_cons	0.7262	0.1462	4.97	0.000		

Fieldwork, 2025

Table 8 summarizes the linear regression analysis examining the impact of organizational factors (Orgf) on Artificial Intelligence adoption (AIadop) among accounting practitioners in Nigerian banks. The results show that the model is statistically significant ($F = 351.67$, $p = 0.000$) and explains a substantial portion of the variance in AI adoption ($R^2 = 0.491$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.4900$). This means that organizational elements such as leadership style, culture, infrastructure, financial commitment, and employee expertise account for about 49% of the differences in how AI technologies are adopted across banks.

The regression coefficient for organizational factors ($\beta = 0.7649$, $p < 0.01$) indicates a strong and positive relationship, implying that improvements in organizational support lead to greater AI adoption. The positive constant ($_cons = 0.7262$, $p = 0.000$) also suggests a baseline tendency toward AI use even when organizational factors are controlled. Overall, the findings emphasize that organizational readiness especially in leadership, culture, and resource allocation is a crucial determinant of successful AI implementation in Nigerian banks.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Despite the acknowledged benefits of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in accounting such as enhanced accuracy, cost and time efficiency, improved fraud detection, risk management, and data-driven decision-making its adoption among Nigerian accounting firms remains relatively slow. Several factors contribute to this challenge, including differences in age, gender, educational background, and professional experience; fear of job redundancy; limited exposure to digital tools; inadequate technological infrastructure; high implementation costs; restricted access to advanced AI-based software; regulatory uncertainty; and insufficient technical expertise. These constraints have collectively hindered the seamless integration of AI technologies into accounting practice in Nigeria.

A key debate in accounting research has been whether specific factors significantly influence the adoption of AI. Unlike many previous studies that employed qualitative approaches with limited empirical validation, this study adopted a quantitative analysis to examine two critical determinants demographic factors and organizational factors affecting AI adoption among accounting practitioners in Nigeria. The findings reveal that both demographic characteristics and organizational conditions play a pivotal role in determining the extent to which AI is embraced within the accounting profession.

Based on these findings, the study recommends the following:

- i. Organizations should promote and recruit accounting professionals who demonstrate a strong interest in technological innovation, particularly in AI tools and applications. This can be achieved by hiring mid-career personnel who typically possess a balance of experience, adaptability, and openness to new technologies.
- ii. Firms should cultivate an organizational culture that supports continuous learning and innovation. This includes creating awareness, offering regular training in machine learning and image recognition, and investing in expert systems and analytical tools to facilitate effective AI integration into accounting processes.

In conclusion, this study provides valuable practical insights into how demographic and organizational factors shape AI adoption within the Nigerian accounting sector. By addressing these determinants through targeted recruitment, skill development, and infrastructural investment, accounting organizations can accelerate the transition toward AI-driven practices and enhance overall efficiency and competitiveness in the digital era.

REFERENCES

- Adelekan, O.A., Adisa, O., Ilugbusi, B.S., Obi, O.C., Awonuga, K.F., Asuzu, O.F. & Ndubuisi, N.L. (2024). Evolving tax compliance in the digital era: A comparative analysis of ai-driven models and blockchain technology in us tax administration. *Computer Science & IT Research Journal*, 5(2), 311-335.
- Agidi, R.C. (2019). Artificial Intelligence in Nigeria Financial Sector'. *I.J. of Electronics and Information Engineering*, 11(1), 40–47.
- Ahmad, H., & Mustafa, H. (2022). The impact of artificial intelligence, big data analytics and business intelligence on transformation capability and digital transformation in Jordanian telecommunication firms. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 6(3), 727-732
- Aziz, L.A.R., & Andriansyah, Y. (2023). The role artificial intelligence in modern banking: an exploration of AI-driven approaches for enhanced fraud prevention, risk management, and regulatory compliance. *Reviews of Contemporary Business Analytics*, 6(1), 110–132.
- Bankins, S., & Formosa, P. (2023). The ethical implications of artificial intelligence (AI) for meaningful work. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 185(4), 725-740.
- Bhalerao, K., Kumar, A., Kumar, A., & Pujari, P. (2022). A Study of Barriers and Benefits of Artificial Intelligence Adoption in Small and Medium Enterprise. *Academy of Marketing Studies Journal*, 26, 1-6.
- Busari, R.R., & Idowu, T.A. (2024). Adoption and Impact of Artificial Intelligence Tools on Audit Practices among Small and Medium Audit Firms in Oyo State. *Nigerian Journal of Management Studies*, 25(2), 50–61.
- Chatterjee, S., Chaudhuri, R., Vrontis, D. Soumya, T. & Ghosh, K. (2021). Adoption of artificial intelligence-integrated CRM systems in agile organizations in India *Technological, Forecasting and Social Change*, 168, 234-256
- Chukwuani, V.N., & Egiyi, M.A. (2020). Automation of accounting processes: impact of artificial intelligence. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 4(8), 444-449.

- Chukwudi, O. (2018). Artificial intelligence system: implication for proper record keeping in microfinance banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 8.
- Dagunduro, M.E, Falana, G.A, Adewara, Y.M, & Busayo, T.O. (2023). Application of artificial intelligence and audit quality in Nigeria. *Humanities, Management, Arts, Education & the Social Sciences Journal*, 11(1):39-56.
- Emetaram, E., & Uchime, H.N. (2021). Impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on accountancy profession. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 7(2), 15–25.
- Falana, G.A., Igbekoyi, O.E. & Dagunduro, M. (2023) Effect of big data on accounting information quality in selected firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 7(3):789-806.
- Haenlein, M. & Kaplan, A. (2019). A brief history of artificial intelligence: On the past, present, and future of artificial intelligence. *California Management Review*, 61(4), 5–14.
- Hassani, H. & MacFeely, S. (2023) Driving Excellence in Official Statistics: Unleashing the Potential of Comprehensive Digital Data Governance. *Big Data Cogn. Comput.* 7, 1-26
- Hassani, H., Unger, S., & Beneki, C. (2020). Big data and actuarial science. big data and cognitive computing, *Journal of Management*, 4(4), 40.
- Ibrahim, K., & Jahswill, G.O. (2024). Effect of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on the Future of Auditing and Assurance Services in Nigeria.
- Izukwe, R., & Jeroh, E. (2022). Auditors' attributes and firm value of listed Nigerian Service firms. *Finance & Accounting Research Journal*, 4(4), 218-230
- Jeroh, E. (2023). The moderating effect of tax aggressiveness on the relationship between corporate governance and real earnings management: Evidence from listed Nigerian firms. *International Journal of Management & Entrepreneurship Research*, 5(5), 314-325,
- Lee, C.S., & Tajudeen, F.P. (2020). Usage and impact of artificial intelligence on accounting: 213 evidence from Malaysian organisations. *Asian Journal of Business and Accounting*, 13(1), 213–240.
- Mutashar, S.S. & Flayyih, H.H. (2024). The impact of artificial intelligence on accounting performance: Sustainable development as a mediating variable. *International Journal of Economics and Finance Studies*, 16(2), 36–54.
- Ogunbangbe, N.B.M. & Kalu. A.O.U. (2024). Artificial intelligence (AI) and financial sector regulation: implications for accountants in Nigeria economy. *Journal of Management and Science*, 14(4), 57–67.
- Oladele, F., Akinsola, T., Afrogha, O., Wright, O., & Oyewole, T. (2021). Accountants' training framework and use of technologies among Nigerian professional accountants. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 1(1), 1–26.
- Owonifari, V.O., Igbekoyi, O.E., Awotomilusi, N.S. & Dagunduro, M.E. (2023). Evaluation of artificial intelligence and efficacy of audit practice in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics*, 23(16), 1–14.
- Oyedokun, G.E., Anyahara, I.O., & Oyedokun, P.O., (2025). Harnessing FinTech and Artificial Intelligence for Financial Inclusion and Entrepreneurial Growth: An Empirical Review. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*, 8(7), 4741-4749,

<https://doi.org/10.47191/jefms/v8-i7-62> ; <https://www.ijefm.co.in/v8i7/62.php>

- Oyedokun, G.E. (2025). Artificial Intelligence and Academic Integrity: A New Frontier in Combating Emerging Threats. In P.A. Okebukola (Ed.). *A handbook on Artificial Intelligence and Quality Higher Education* Volume 3, 189-196. Book in honour of Abubakar Adamu Rasheed. ISBN- 978-93-93853-84-4. Published by Sterling Publishers, Slough UK and Delhi, India
- Peng, Y., & Chang, J. S. (2019). An exploration on the problems of replacing accounting professions by AI in the future. *Proceedings of the 2019 5th International Conference on Industrial and Business Engineering*. New York, NY, USA: ACM.
- Petkov, R. (2020). Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the accounting function - A revisit and a new perspective for developing framework. *Journal of Emerging Technologies in Accounting*, 17(1), 99-105.
- Rawashdeh, A., Bakhit, M., & Abaalkhail, L. (2023). Determinants of artificial intelligence adoption in SMEs: The mediating role of accounting automation. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 7(1), 25–34.
- Ukpong, E. (2022). Integration of Artificial Intelligence Applications for financial process innovation by commercial banks in Nigeria. *AKSU Journal* 2(1), 125-137
- Venkatesh, N., Morris, N., Davis, N., & Davis, N. (2003). User acceptance of information Technology: toward a unified view. *MIS Quarterly*, 27(3), 425.
- Victor, O.O., Olusola, E.I., Niyi, S.A. & Muyiwa, E.D. (2023) Evaluation of artificial intelligence and efficacy of audit practice in Nigeria *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 23(16), 1-14.